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AN OVERVIEW ON 1,2,4-TRIAZOLE AND 1,3,4-THIADIAZOLE DERIVATIVES AS POTENTIAL ANESTHESIC AND ANTI-INFLAMMATORY AGENTS

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The aim. The purpose of this review is to summarize data on the synthesis and structural modification of heterocyclic systems with triazole and thiazole fragments in molecules as promising objects in bioorganic and medicinal chemistry.

Materials and methods. The research based on bibliosemantic and analytical methods using bibliographic and abstract databases, as well as databases of chemical compounds.

Results. Modern medicinal chemistry faces many challenges, one of which is the determination of the activity and specificity of therapeutic agents. Recent scientific data showed that triazoles and/or thiazoles have broad spectrum of biological activities, in particular antimicrobial, antifungal, antiviral, anticancer and anticonvulsant. Synthetic research allows to propose a whole number of new molecular design directions of biological active triazole and/or thiazole derivatives, as well as to obtain directed library that include hundreds of new compounds. This review is an effort to summarize data of its analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity over the last decade. We summarized and analyzed the series of triazole and/or thiazole derivatives and provided data of their structure-activity relationship. For optimization and rational design of highly active molecules with optimal «drug-like» characteristics and discovering of possible mechanism of action SAR, QSAR analysis and molecular docking were summarized.

Conclusions. It has been shown that heterocyclic systems containing fragments of triazole and/or thiazole are a significant source of promising analgesic and/or anti-inflammatory agents. It has been established that the mentioned heterocyclic derivatives have a high selectivity of action, low toxicity and an effect commensurate with standard drugs

Keywords: heterocycles, triazoles, thiazoles, anti-inflammatory activity, analgetic activity, NSAIDs

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1. Introduction

In recent years, heterocyclic compounds and their analogues are of considerable interest due to the wide range of their useful biological and pharmacological properties. Thus, different classes of heterocyclic systems underlie most existing drugs or compounds that are in the final stages of preclinical trials [1–5]. The particular interest in this context is the study of heterocyclic compounds based on azole core, which has significant synthetic and pharmacological potential [6–10]. The uniqueness of these heterocycle systems is based on easy functionalization with the possibility of obtaining various condensed [11–17] and non-condensed derivatives [18–23]. In addition, the use of modern approaches for studying this class heterocycles such as target-oriented [24–26] and diversity-oriented synthesis (DOS) approaches [27–30] are an opportunity to obtain combinatorial libraries to effectively searching new drugs or drug candidates.

The triazole core is present in various compounds characterized by pronounced antimicrobial [31–33], antifungal [32, 33], antiviral [34], anti-HIV-1 [35], antimycobacterial [31, 34], antihistamine [36], anticonvulsant [37–40], anti-tumor [33, 35], insecticidal [41], anxiolytic [42], analgesic [43]

activities. On the other hand, thiazole derivatives are relevant for the searching agents with antifungal [44], antimicrobial [45, 46], antitumor [47], anticonvulsant [48], antiviral [46], antibacterial [44] activities. Triazoles and thiazoles exhibit a wide range of biological activity presented in various drugs, such as Trazodone (an antidepressant), Rizatriptan (an analgesic for treatment of headaches, including migraines), Hexaconazole (an antifungal agent) and Alprazolam (sedative and tranquilizer). The known modifications of the triazole or thiazole ring have proven to be effective with greater efficiency and less toxicity. At the same time, the number of triazole and thiazole-base drugs currently used in the clinic as analgesics is quite small. These include Rizatriptan, which has been shown to be effective for headaches of various origins [49–54]. Given the abovementioned, triazole and thiazole derivatives are of interest for the search for anti-inflammatory drugs in view of both pharmacological potential and chemical novelty for modern medicinal chemistry and pharmacology.

The aim of the study was to analyze the literature data about the synthesis and biological activity evaluation of heterocyclic compounds with triazole and thiazole fragments in molecules.

2. Materials and methods

Bibliosemantic and analytical methods were used in the study. During the literature review were used also bibliographic and abstract databases (Pubmed), as well as databases of chemical compounds (PubChem, Reaxys and SciFinder).

3. Results and discussion

The potential nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory agents among triazolo-thiadiazole derivatives are of interest to many scientific groups [55]. Thus, *N*-[5-(4-amino-5-mercapto-4*H*-[1,2,4]triazolo-3-yl)-4-methyl-1,3-thiazol-2-yl]acetamide derivatives showed antiexudative activity comparable to reference drug diclofenac. Moreover, [1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-*b*][3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazine derivatives **1** obtained via condensation reaction of chloroacetic acid and α -haloketones also showed a significant antibacterial effect [43]. [2,1-*b*]Furan-2-yl-5-*H*-aryl-[1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazole-6(5*H*)-thione **2** and [2,1-*b*]furan-2-yl-5,6-diaryl-5,6-dihydro[1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazole **3** derivatives possessed analgesic activity comparable to acetylsalicylic acid, under a single intragastric injection to nonlinear mice at a dose of 100 mg/kg in the model on acetic acid-induced writhing response in mice [56].

The authors [57] observed moderate antiexudative and significant antinociceptive activity of 3- β -[(*N*-benzenesulfonyl/tosyl)-4-phenylamino]ethyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-4(*H*)-1,2,4-triazoles **4**. Studied derivatives also showed a significant anti-exudative effect in the model of carrageenan edema in rats at the level of acetylsalicylic acid, as well as in the model of cotton granuloma. Moreover, the synthesized compounds did not have ulcerogenic action in experimental animals. The significant activity of these derivatives was demonstrated in the model of thermal nociceptive stimulation of tail flick, with 81.02–120.72 % inhibition compared with aspirin (49.39 % inhibition). The authors established the analgesic effect of target compounds related with a presence of biologically active sulfonamide fragment in the structure.

Synthesized 5-carbomethoxy-2-substituted-7*H*-1,2,4-triazolo[3,2-*b*]-1,3-thiazin-7-one derivatives **5** showed pronounced anti-inflammatory activity under oral administration in low doses (10 and 20 mg/kg) in models of carrageenan and serotonin edema which were equal or higher to diclofenac sodium. It should be noted that the anti-exudative activity correlated with the analgesic effect in the model of acetic acid-induced writhing response in mice. In addition, these biological effects were not accompanied by gastric lesions [58].

A pronounced antinociceptive effect was found for 3-(4-methylphenyl)-4-[3-(phenoxyethyl)-7*H*-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*][3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazine-6-yl]-1,2,3-oxadiazol-5-olates **6**, which exceed the activity of paracetamol [59] (Fig. 1).

Condensed 1,2,4-triazoles with a 2,4-dichlorophenoxy moiety in molecules **7** showed anti-inflammatory activity under intragastrically administration in equal doses to indomethacin [60]. These compounds showed a dose-dependent anti-inflammatory effect in carrageenan and histamine edema models. Condensed derivatives with 2,4-dichlorophenoxy group at position 6 showed the highest activity comparable to indomethacin, with 36–56 % inhibition of exudative inflammation.

3-(*N*-substituted carboxamidoethylthio)-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole derivatives **8** under administration intraperitoneally to rats at a dose of 40 mg/kg showed a significant antiexudative effect in the model of formalin edema with 25.92%–44.44 % inhibition which exceeds reference drug diclofenac sodium (23.14 %). The anti-exudative effect of the studied compounds depends on the presence of chloro-, nitro-, methyl- or methoxy groups in the phenyl substituent. Several mentioned compounds also showed an antinociceptive effect on the hot plate model (up to 303.4 %), which exceeds the parameters of tramadol (169.4 %). In addition, the most active derivatives did not show anxiolytic activity [61].

Fig. 1. Structures of derivatives 1–6

The authors [62] studied 1,3,4-thiadiazole and 1,2,4-triazole derivatives containing a phenylalanine moiety **9**. The studied derivatives had low toxicity (LD₅₀ 1025–5010 mg/kg when administered intragastrically). When administered target derivatives at doses of 1/10 LD₅₀ and 1/5 LD₅₀ in the nystatin edema model, the compounds generally exceeded acetylsalicylic acid and phenylbutazone at the respective doses, but possess less activity than indomethacin.

Triazole-containing tetracyclic thienopyrimidines have proven to be promising as potential anti-inflammatory and analgesic agents [63]. The administration orally of mentioned compounds at doses of 10 mg/kg, predominate or are equivalent in analgesic and antiexudative activity diclofenac sodium in carrageenan edema (edema inhibition from –31.2 % to –56.1 %) and acetic acid-induced writhing response (degree of inhibition from 45.3 % – up to 71.7 %) models in mice. It worth mentioned that the tested compounds did not have ulcerogenic effect.

The authors [64] synthesized a series of 3-[2-(*N*-methylamino)phenyl]-6-[2-(2-(2,4-dichlorophenoxy)ethyl)-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazole derivatives **10** to assess their biological activity. Synthesized compounds were tested for anti-inflammatory activity in rats using carrageenan-induced paw edema model in rats. However, the tested compounds showed weak antiexudative activity than reference drug (diclofenac sodium). The evaluation their analgesic activity on hot-plate test led to identification the most active compound 3-[4-(*N,N*-dimethylamino)phenyl]-6-[2-(2,4-dichlorophenoxy)ethyl]-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazole, which was selected for further in-depth study.

In another study [65], the same authors studied triazolothiadiazole derivatives which contain an indole ring in structure. These derivatives show significant analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity, especially 3-(2-chloro-5-methoxyphenyl)-6-((5-methoxy-1*H*-indol-3-yl)methyl)-[1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazole. The SAR-analysis showed that the introduction of electron donor groups (methyl, methoxyl) at position 5 of the indole ring leads to a decrease of anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity.

It is shown that the presence of a trichlorophenyl fragment in triazolothiadiazole and triazolothiadiazine core provides significant anti-inflammatory activity of tested compounds in the model of acute inflammation [66]. Derivative A-561 (6-(4-methoxyphenyl)-3-(2,3,5-trichlorophenyl)-[1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazole) **11** showed the highest level of biological activity.

The authors [67] reported the synthesis of several triazole derivatives **12** and screening for their anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity. Among the fused derivatives, compounds with 3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl and 4-fluorophenyl groups at position 6 of the basic cycle possessed the highest dose-dependent anti-inflammatory activity (Fig. 2). Thus, among the synthesized compounds 3-[2-(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)ethyl]-6-(4-chlorophenyl)-7*H*-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazine showed the highest analgesic activity in the experiment, which was close to the effect of ketorolac. The SAR-analysis revealed that the presence of methoxy groups is favourable on the presence of analgesic activity.

Synthesized 3,6-disubstituted-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazole derivatives were evaluated for anti-inflammatory activity in the model of carrageenan and formalin edema. The studied derivatives showed a pronounced anti-exudative effect. In particular, 3-(phenoxyethyl)-6-(3-oxo-3-phenylpropyl)-[1,2,4]triazolo[3,4][1,3,4]thiadiazoles possess prominent anti-inflammatory activity comparable to reference drug indomethacin. The SAR-analysis showed that the replacement of 3-oxo-3-phenylpropyl group in the C-6 position by other groups led to decreasing of anti-inflammatory activity. In addition, the synthesized compounds exhibited the higher level of antiexudative activity than phenoxyacetic and salicylic acid derivatives [68]. The study of analgesic activity on acetic acid-induced writhing response in mice model was shown that synthesized compounds which include 3-oxo-3-phenylpropyl group in the C-3 position of the triazolothiadiazole ring showed high level of analgesic activity comparable to standard drug (acetylsalicylic acid).

The authors [69] reported *in vitro* and *in vivo* screening for the anti-inflammatory activity of a series of pyridine-substituted triazoles and thiadiazoles **13** on carrageenan-induced paw edema model. *In vivo* experiments were performed on albino rats using indomethacin as a reference drug. 3,6-Di(pyridin-4-yl)-[1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazole showed maximum anti-inflammatory activity.

Authors [70] synthesized and evaluated biological activity of 3,6-disubstituted-1,2,4-triazolothiadiazole derivatives which contain pyrazole fragment in structure. The screening results showed that 3-propyl-6-(3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-[1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazoles **14** po-

Fig. 2. Structures of derivatives 7–12

essed significant antiexudative activity on carrageenan-induced paw edema and serotonin edema models comparable to reference drug diclofenac sodium.

The authors [71] reported synthesis of several triazolothiadiazole derivatives **15** that showed significant analgesic activity in a model of visceral pain caused by intra-abdominal acetic acid in mice (modified by R. Koster, 1959). The results showed that the highest analgesic activity showed 5-methoxy-2-(3-((5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-naphthalen-2-yloxy)methyl)-7H-[1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-*b*] [1,3,4]thiadiazin-6-yl)phenol, with antinociceptive effect higher than acetylsalicylic acid. It worth mentioned that, the presence of hydroxyl and methoxy groups in the phenyl ring at position 6 may cause good analgesic activity.

Interesting data are given by the authors [72], who report the study of the activity of numerous triazole and thiadiazole derivatives **16**. The synthesized compounds were studied for analgesic activity in the hot plate model. The screening results led identification of active compounds, namely 6-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)-3-(2,4-dichloro-5-fluorophenyl)-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazole and 3-(2,4-dichloro-5-fluorophenyl)-6-[(4-pephenoxy)methyl]-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazole. The analgesic activity of these derivatives depends on the presence of halogen substituent (chlorine and fluorine) on both aryl rings in positions 3 and 6.

The results of a study of recently synthesized derivatives of triazolethiadiazole and triazolothiadiazines **17**, including 3-nitronaphtho[2,1-*b*]furan moiety, showed a significant antinociceptive effect of these heterocyclic compounds [73] (Fig. 3). The activity of the synthesized derivatives was comparable to the standard drug (tramadol). In addition, triazolethiadiazole and triazolothiadiazine derivatives possess other types of biological activities, namely anticancer [74–76], antileishmanial [77] and antimicrobial [78–83].

It should be noted that molecular docking studies against COX-2 [84–87], 15-LOX [88], p38 α MAP kinase [89, 90] and TNF- α [91] biotargets of triazole and

thiadiazole derivatives are correlated with experimental data confirming the significant analgesic and anti-inflammatory potential of mentioned compounds.

Fig. 3. Structures of derivatives 13–17

4. Conclusion

We reviewed data on the anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity of compounds containing triazole and/or thiadiazole fragment in molecules. Data analysis showed that these derivatives are characterized by significant antinociceptive and antiexudative effects, which are often accompanied by low toxicity, lack of ulcerogenic action, which reveal the significant interest to pharmacy and medicine. The activity profile of these derivatives is based on the nature of the substituent of the basic triazole and/or thiadiazole core. The use of the obtained literature data and their systematic analysis could be promising for the rational design of potential biologically active molecules and further study of the pharmacological effect of mentioned derivatives.

Conflict of interests

The authors declare there is no conflict of interests.

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References

- Gomtsyan, A. (2012). Heterocycles in drugs and drug discovery. *Chemistry of Heterocyclic Compounds*, 48 (1), 7–10. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s10593-012-0960-z>
- Heravi, M. M., Zadsirjan, V. (2020). Prescribed drugs containing nitrogen heterocycles: an overview. *RSC Advances*, 10 (72), 44247–44311. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1039/d0ra09198g>
- Broughton, H. B., Watson, I. A. (2004). Selection of heterocycles for drug design. *Journal of Molecular Graphics and Modelling*, 23 (1), 51–58. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.jm gm.2004.03.016>
- Taylor, A. P., Robinson, R. P., Fobian, Y. M., Blakemore, D. C., Jones, L. H., Fadeyi, O. (2016). Modern advances in heterocyclic chemistry in drug discovery. *Organic & Biomolecular Chemistry*, 14 (28), 6611–6637. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1039/c6ob00936k>

30. Spring, D. R. (2003). Diversity-oriented synthesis; a challenge for synthetic chemists. *Organic & biomolecular chemistry*, 1 (22), 3867–3870. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1039/b310752n>
31. Shiradkar, M., Pandit, U., Akula, K. C., Maheta, A., Kumar, G. V. S. (2007). Microwave assisted synthesis and antimicrobial screening of fused triazoles. *Arkivoc*, 2006 (14), 141–154. doi: <http://doi.org/10.3998/ark.5550190.0007.e16>
32. Lingappa, B., Girisha, K. S., Kalluraya, B., Rai, N. S., Kumari, N. S. (2008). Regioselective reaction: synthesis of novel Mannich bases derived from 3-(4,6-disubstituted-2-thiomethylpyrimidyl)-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles and their antimicrobial properties. *Indian Journal of Chemistry*, 47B, 1858–1864.
33. Gautam, N., Chourasia, O. P. (2010). Synthesis, antimicrobial and insecticidal activity of some 4H-1,2,4 triazole derivatives. *Indian Journal of Chemistry*, 49B, 956–959.
34. Kumar, P. V., Rao, V. R. (2008). Synthesis and antitubercular, antiviral and anticancer activity of 3-(3-mercaptoalkyl-7H-[1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]-thiadiazin-6-yl)chromen-2-one and its derivatives. *Indian Journal of Chemistry*, 47B, 106–111.
35. Wu, J., Liu, X., Cheng, X., Cao, Y., Wang, D., Li, Z. et al. (2007). Synthesis of Novel Derivatives of 4-Amino-3-(2-Furyl)-5-Mercapto-1,2,4-Triazole as Potential HIV-1 NNRTIs. *Molecules*, 12 (8), 2003–2016. doi: <http://doi.org/10.3390/12082003>
36. Fathalla, W., Rayes, S. M. E., Ali, I. A. I. (2007). Convenient synthesis of 1-substituted-4-methyl-5-oxo [1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]quinazolines. *Arkivoc*, 2007 (16), 173–186. doi: <http://doi.org/10.3998/ark.5550190.0008.g18>
37. Chen, J., Sun, X.-Y., Chai, K.-Y., Lee, J.-S., Song, M.-S., Quan, Z.-S. (2007). Synthesis and anticonvulsant evaluation of 4-(4-alkoxyphenyl)-3-ethyl-4H-1,2,4-triazoles as open-chain analogues of 7-alkoxyl-4,5-dihydro[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]quinolines. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, 15 (21), 6775–6781. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmc.2007.08.004>
38. Kavraiskiy, D. P., Shtrygol', S. Yu., Georgiyants, V. A., Saidov, N. B. (2016). Screening investigation of novel 1,2,4-triazole-3-thione derivatives on anticonvulsant activity. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Chemistry*, 2 (2), 47–51.
39. Glushchenko, A. V., Rybalchenko, T. L., Shtrygol, S. Yu., Georgiyants, V. A., Perekhoda, L. A. (2010). Anticonvulsant activity of derivatives 1-substitute 5-methyl(amino)-1,2,3-triazole. *Ukrainian biopharmaceutical journal*, 3 (8), 28–34.
40. Rybalchenko, T. L., Shtrygol, S. Y., Georgiyants, V. A. (2014). Definition of spectrum of the anticonvulsant activity for the new anticonvulsants – 1,2,3-triazole and 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives. *Belgorod State University Scientific bulletin. Medicine Pharmacy*, 11 (182), 26/1, 199–203.
41. Zhao, X.-L., Zhao, Y.-F., Guo, S.-C., Song, H.-S., Wang, D., Gong, P. (2007). Synthesis and Anti-tumor Activities of Novel [1,2,4]triazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidines. *Molecules*, 12 (5), 1136–1146. doi: <http://doi.org/10.3390/12051136>
42. Manikrao, A. M., Fursule, R. A., Rajesh, K. S., Kunjwani, H. K., Sabale, P. M. (2010). Synthesis and biological screening of novel derivatives of 3-(N-substituted carboxamidoethylthio)-(4H)-1,2,4-triazoles. *Indian Journal of Chemistry*, 49B, 1642–1647.
43. Ramakrishna, M., Himabindu, V., Reddy, T. M., Chakravarthy, A. K. (2011). s-Triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazoles, s-Triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazines and s-Triazolo[3',4':2,3]thiadiazino[5,6-b]quinoxaline Derivatives of Clubbed Triazole: Novel Pharmacophore as Dual Inhibitors. *Asian Journal of Chemistry*, 23 (1), 439.
44. Sukla, D. K., Srivastava, S. D. (2008). Synthesis of some new 5-[(1,2,3-benzotriazole)-1-yl-methyl]-1'-(4'-substituted aryl)-3'-chloro-2'-oxo azetidines} amino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles: antifungal and antibacterial agents. *Indian Journal of Chemistry*, 47B, 463–469.
45. Demirbas, N., Karaoglu, S. A., Demirbas, A., Çelik, E. (2005). Synthesis and antimicrobial activities of some new [1,2,4] triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazoles and [1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-b] [1,3,4]thiadiazines. *Arkivoc*, 2005 (1), 75–91. doi: <http://doi.org/10.3998/ark.5550190.0006.108>
46. Farghaly, A.-R., Clercq, E. D., El-Kashef, H. (2006). Synthesis and antiviral activity of novel [1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazoles, [1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-b] [1,3,4]thiadiazines and [1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazepines. *Arkivoc*, 2006 (10), 137–151. doi: <http://doi.org/10.3998/ark.5550190.0007.a17>
47. Matysiak, J., Nasulewicz, A., Pełczyńska, M., Świtalska, M., Jaroszewicz, I., Opolski, A. (2006). Synthesis and antiproliferative activity of some 5-substituted 2-(2,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazoles. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 41 (4), 475–482. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2005.12.007>
48. Pattanayak, P., Sharma R. 2-Amino-5-sulphonyl 1,3,4-thiadiazole derivatives as anticonvulsant agents: Synthesis and Evaluation (2010). *Indian Journal of Chemistry*, 49B, 1531–1534.
49. Teall, J., Tuchman, M., Cutler, N., Gross, M., Willoughby, E. et al. (1998). Rizatriptan (MAXALT) for the Acute Treatment of Migraine and Migraine Recurrence. A Placebo-Controlled, Outpatient Study. *Headache: The Journal of Head and Face Pain*, 38 (4), 281–287. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1046/j.1526-4610.1998.3804281.x>
50. Dooley, M., Faulds, D. (1999). Rizatriptan: a review of its efficacy in the management of migraine. *Drugs*, 58 (4), 699–723. doi: <http://doi.org/10.2165/00003495-199958040-00013>
51. Silberstein, S. D., Massiou, H., Le Jeune, C., Johnson-Pratt, L., Mccarroll, K. A., Lines, C. R. (2000). Rizatriptan in the Treatment of Menstrual Migraine. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 96 (2), 237–242. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1097/00006250-200008000-00016>
52. Láinez, M. J. (2006). Rizatriptan in the treatment of migraine. *Neuropsychiatric Disease and Treatment*, 2 (3), 247–259. doi: <http://doi.org/10.2147/ndt.2006.2.3.247>
53. Winner, P., Lewis, D., Visser, W. H., Jiang, K., Ahrens, S., Evans, J. K. (2002). Rizatriptan 5 mg for the Acute Treatment of Migraine in Adolescents: A Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled Study. *Headache: The Journal of Head and Face Pain*, 42 (1), 49–55. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1046/j.1526-4610.2002.02013.x>
54. Ahonen, K., Hamalainen, M. L., Eerola, M., Hoppu, K. (2006). A randomized trial of rizatriptan in migraine attacks in children. *Neurology*, 67 (7), 1135–1140. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1212/01.wnl.0000238179.79888.44>

55. Sahu, J. K., Ganguly, S., Kaushik, A. (2013). Triazoles: A valuable insight into recent developments and biological activities. *Chinese Journal of Natural Medicines*, 11 (5), 456–465. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1016/s1875-5364\(13\)60084-9](http://doi.org/10.1016/s1875-5364(13)60084-9)
56. Ravindra, K. C., Vagdevi, H. M., Vaidya, V. P. (2008). Synthesis, characterization and pharmacological studies on some triazolothiadiazines and triazolothiadiazoles containing naphtho[2,b]furan. *Indian Journal of Chemistry*, 47B, 1271–1276.
57. Desai, S., Bennur, R., Bennur, S., Laddi, U., Patil, P. (2011). Synthesis and pharmacological activities of some new 3-Substituted-4-Amino-5-Mercapto-1,2,4-Triazoles. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 73 (1), 115–120. doi: <http://doi.org/10.4103/0250-474x.89771>
58. Tozkoparan, B., Aktay, G., Yeşilada, E. (2002). Synthesis of some 1,2,4-triazolo[3,2-b]-1,3-thiazine-7-ones with potential analgesic and antiinflammatory activities. *Il Farmaco*, 57 (2), 145–152. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1016/s0014-827x\(01\)01195-8](http://doi.org/10.1016/s0014-827x(01)01195-8)
59. Goh, J. H., Fun, H.-K., Nithinchandra, Kalluraya, B. (2010). 4-[3-(Phenoxyethyl)-7H-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazin-6-yl]-3-(p-tolyl)sydnone. *Acta Crystallographica Section E Structure Reports Online*, 66 (8), o2178–o2179. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1107/s1600536810029910>
60. El Shehry, M. F., Abu-Hashem, A. A., El-Telbani, E. M. (2010). Synthesis of 3-((2,4-dichlorophenoxy)methyl)-1,2,4-triazolo(thiadiazoles and thiadiazines) as anti-inflammatory and molluscicidal agents. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 45 (5), 1906–1911. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2010.01.030>
61. Mahajan, N. S., Manikrao, A. M., Shinde, P. N., Jawarkar, R. D., Khatale, P. N., Dhawale, S. C. (2012). A Review: Biological Importance of Mercapto Substituted 1,2,4-triazole Derivatives. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*, 5 (7), 863–876.
62. Moise, M., Sunel, V., Profire, L., Popa, M., Desbrieres, J., Peptu, C. (2009). Synthesis and Biological Activity of Some New 1,3,4-Thiadiazole and 1,2,4-Triazole Compounds Containing a Phenylalanine Moiety. *Molecules*, 14 (7), 2621–2631. doi: <http://doi.org/10.3390/molecules14072621>
63. Mulla, J. A. S., Khazi, M. I. A., Panchamukhi, S. I., Gong, Y.-D., Khazi, I. A. M. (2014). Synthesis and pharmacological evaluation of novel thienopyrimidine and triazolothienopyrimidine derivatives. *Medicinal Chemistry Research*, 23 (6), 3235–3243. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00044-013-0900-1>
64. Mathew, V., Keshavayya, J., Vaidya, V. P. (2006). Heterocyclic system containing bridgehead nitrogen atom: synthesis and pharmacological activities of some substituted 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 41 (9), 1048–1058. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2006.03.018>
65. Mathew, V., Keshavayya, J., Vaidya, V. P., Giles, D. (2007). Studies on synthesis and pharmacological activities of 3,6-disubstituted-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles and their dihydro analogues. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 42 (6), 823–840. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2006.12.010>
66. Karegoudar, P., Prasad, D. J., Ashok, M., Mahalinga, M., Poojary, B., Holla, B. S. (2008). Synthesis, antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory activities of some 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazoles and 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazines bearing trichlorophenyl moiety. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 43 (4), 808–815. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2007.06.026>
67. Aytaç, S. P., Tozkoparan, B., Kaynak, F. B., Aktay, G., Göktaş, Ö., Ünüvar, S. (2009). Synthesis of 3,6-disubstituted 7H-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazines as novel analgesic/anti-inflammatory compounds. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 44 (11), 4528–4538. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2009.06.026>
68. Husain, A., Naseer, M. A. (2009). Studies on fused heterocyclic 3,6-disubstituted-1,2,4-triazolo-1,3,4-thiadiazoles: synthesis and biological evaluation. *Medicinal Chemistry Research*, 20 (1), 47–54. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00044-009-9281-x>
69. Hussein, M. A., Shaker, R. M., Ameen, M. A., Mohammed, M. F. (2011). Synthesis, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and antibacterial activities of some triazole, triazolothiadiazole, and triazolothiadiazine derivatives. *Archives of Pharmacal Research*, 34 (8), 1239–1250. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s12272-011-0802-z>
70. Malladi, S., Isloor, A. M., Shetty, P., Fun, H. K., Telkar, S., Mahmood, R., Isloor, N. (2011). Synthesis and anti-inflammatory evaluation of some new 3,6-disubstituted-1,2,4-triazolo-[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles bearing pyrazole moiety. *Medicinal Chemistry Research*, 21 (10), 3272–3280. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00044-011-9865-0>
71. Turan-Zitouni, G., Kaplancikli, Z., Erol, K., Kiliç, F. (1999). Synthesis and analgesic activity of some triazoles and triazolothiadiazines. *Il Farmaco*, 54 (4), 218–223. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1016/s0014-827x\(99\)00016-6](http://doi.org/10.1016/s0014-827x(99)00016-6)
72. Karthikeyan, M. S., Holla, B. S., Kalluraya, B., Kumari, N. S. (2007). Biological Studies of Some 2,4-Dichloro-5-fluorophenyl Containing Triazolothiadiazoles. *Monatshefte Für Chemie – Chemical Monthly*, 138 (12), 1309–1316. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00706-007-0718-y>
73. Khan, I., Ibrar, A., Abbas, N. (2013). Triazolothiadiazoles and triazolothiadiazines – Biologically attractive scaffolds. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 63, 854–868. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2013.01.060>
74. Kamel, M. M., Megally Abdo, N. Y. (2014). Synthesis of novel 1,2,4-triazoles, triazolothiadiazines and triazolothiadiazoles as potential anticancer agents. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 86, 75–80. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2014.08.047>
75. Boraie, A. T. A., Ghabbour, H. A., Gomaa, M. S., El Ashry, E. S. H., Barakat, A. (2019). Synthesis and Anti-Proliferative Assessment of Triazolo-Thiadiazepine and Triazolo-Thiadiazine Scaffolds. *Molecules*, 24 (24), 4471. doi: <http://doi.org/10.3390/molecules24244471>
76. Ma, W., Chen, P., Huo, X., Ma, Y., Li, Y., Diao, P. et al. (2020). Development of triazolothiadiazine derivatives as highly potent tubulin polymerization inhibitors: Structure-activity relationship, in vitro and in vivo study. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 208, 112847. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2020.112847>
77. Ibrar, A., Zaib, S., Jabeen, F., Iqbal, J., Saeed, A. (2016). Unraveling the Alkaline Phosphatase Inhibition, Anticancer, and Antileishmanial Potential of Coumarin-Triazolothiadiazine Hybrids: Design, Synthesis, and Molecular Docking Analysis. *Archiv Der Pharmazie*, 349 (7), 553–565. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1002/ardp.201500392>

78. Kaplancıklı, Z. A., Turan-Zitouni, G., Özdemir, A., Revial, G. (2008). New triazole and triazolothiadiazine derivatives as possible antimicrobial agents. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 43 (1), 155–159. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2007.03.019>
79. Suresh Kumar, G. V., Rajendra Prasad, Y., Mallikarjuna, B. P., Chandrashekar, S. M. (2010). Synthesis and pharmacological evaluation of clubbed isopropylthiazole derived triazolothiadiazoles, triazolothiadiazines and mannich bases as potential antimicrobial and antitubercular agents. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 45 (11), 5120–5129. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2010.08.023>
80. Abdelhameed, R. M., El-Sayed, H. A., El-Shahat, M., El-Sayed, A. A., Darwesh, O. M. (2018). Novel Triazolothiadiazole and Triazolothiadiazine Derivatives Containing Pyridine Moiety: Design, Synthesis, Bactericidal and Fungicidal Activities. *Current Bioactive Compounds*, 14 (2), 169–179. doi: <http://doi.org/10.2174/1573407213666170127095158>
81. Husain, A., Asif, M., Bhutani, R., Dutta, M. (2013). Triazolothiadiazoles as antimicrobial agent: a short review. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 1 (4), 138–150.
82. Appell, M., Compton, D. L., Evans, K. O. (2020). Predictive Quantitative Structure–Activity Relationship Modeling of the Anti-fungal and Antibiotic Properties of Triazolothiadiazine Compounds. *Methods and Protocols*, 4 (1), 2. doi: <http://doi.org/10.3390/mps4010002>
83. Sim, K.-M., Teo, K.-C. (2018). Synthesis, Characterization and Antibacterial Evaluation of some New 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazines as Potential Antibacterial Agents. *Letters in Drug Design & Discovery*, 15 (7), 733–743. doi: <http://doi.org/10.2174/1570180814666170922165933>
84. Zhang, H.-J., Wang, X.-Z., Cao, Q., Gong, G.-H., Quan, Z.-S. (2017). Design, synthesis, anti-inflammatory activity, and molecular docking studies of perimidine derivatives containing triazole. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters*, 27 (18), 4409–4414. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmcl.2017.08.014>
85. Kishore Kumar, A., Sunitha, V., Shankar, B., Ramesh, M., Murali Krishna, T., Jalapathi, P. (2016). Synthesis, biological evaluation, and molecular docking studies of novel 1,2,3-triazole derivatives as potent anti-inflammatory agents. *Russian Journal of General Chemistry*, 86 (5), 1154–1162. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1134/s1070363216050297>
86. Mehta, D. K., Taya, P., Das, R., Dua, K. (2019). Design, Synthesis and Molecular Docking Studies of Novel Thiadiazole Analogues with Potential Antimicrobial and Antiinflammatory Activities. *Anti-Inflammatory & Anti-Allergy Agents in Medicinal Chemistry*, 18 (2), 91–109. doi: <http://doi.org/10.2174/1871520619666190307162442>
87. Shkair, A. M., Shakya, A. K., Raghavendra, N. M., Naik, R. R. (2016). Molecular Modeling, Synthesis and Pharmacological Evaluation of 1,3,4-Thiadiazoles as Anti-inflammatory and Analgesic Agents. *Medicinal Chemistry*, 12 (1), 90–100. doi: <http://doi.org/10.2174/1573406411666150608102236>
88. Omar, Y. M., Abdu-Allah, H. H. M., Abdel-Moty, S. G. (2018). Synthesis, biological evaluation and docking study of 1,3,4-thiadiazole-thiazolidinone hybrids as anti-inflammatory agents with dual inhibition of COX-2 and 15-LOX. *Bioorganic Chemistry*, 80, 461–471. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioorg.2018.06.036>
89. Tariq, S., Alam, O., Amir, M. (2018). Synthesis, anti-inflammatory, p38 α MAP kinase inhibitory activities and molecular docking studies of quinoxaline derivatives containing triazole moiety. *Bioorganic Chemistry*, 76, 343–358. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioorg.2017.12.003>
90. Tariq, S., Alam, O., Amir, M. (2018). Synthesis, p38 α MAP kinase inhibition, anti-inflammatory activity, and molecular docking studies of 1,2,4-triazole-based benzothiazole-2-amines. *Archiv Der Pharmazie*, 351 (3-4), 1700304. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1002/ardp.201700304>
91. Haider, S., Alam, M. S., Hamid, H., Dhulap, A., Kumar, D. (2019). Design, synthesis and biological evaluation of benzoxazolone-containing 1,3,4-thiadiazoles as TNF- α inhibitors. *Heliyon*, 5 (4), e01503. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e01503>

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